

Synthesis of Pyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine, Thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines and 4-Substituted-pyrimidines

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4-Arylamino-pyrimidines (1c-e), pyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine (4) and thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-7,7-dioxide (3c) were readily synthesised from 4-chloro-2-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-acetyl 6-methylpyrimidine (1b).

IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of pyrimidine derivatives and its fused systems¹ which exhibit interesting biological as well as medicinal applications², we have synthesised some fused pyrimidines.

Results and Discussion

2-(4-Chlorophenyl)-4-chloro-5-acetyl-6-methylpyrimidine (1b) which appeared to be versatile starting material for further functionalisation and annelation of the pyrimidine ring, has been synthesised from 4-mercapto-5-acetylpyrimidine (1a) by its reaction with chlorine³.

In a typical example, treatment of 1b with arylamines, namely aniline, anthranilic acid and ethyl anthranilate resulted in dechloroamination, affording the corresponding arylaminopyrimidines (1c-e). The structure was confirmed by the independent synthesis from 4-methylthiopyrimidine (1f) with arylamine in methanol containing 50% hydrochloric acid⁴. Compound 1e was hydrolysed into the corresponding acid derivative 1d.

Hydrazinolysis of 1b with alcoholic hydrazine afforded the bis-compound 5 instead of the expected pyrazolopyrimidine 2. The latter was synthesised by the reaction of 4-methylthiopyrimidine (1f) with hydrazine hydrate. The reaction of 1b with phenylhydrazine afforded 4-(2-phenylhydrazino)pyrimidine (1g) which gave the correct ion peak in its mass spectra (m/z , 353, M^+).

Treatment of the 4-chloropyrimidine derivative (1b) with urea in refluxing ethanol afforded the pyrimidopyrimidine (4), while subjecting 1b to the action of thiourea in refluxing ethanol afforded the mercaptopyrimidine derivative (1a)⁴. Compound 4 showed a strong bands at 1 660 (C=O) and 3 350 cm^{-1} (NH).

4-Methylthiopyrimidine derivative (1f) reacted with ethyl glycinate hydrochloride in ethanol to give 4-methylaminopyrimidine (1h) instead of the expected 4-carbomethoxymethylaminopyrimidine derivative; the structure was established by its independent synthesis by reaction of 1b with methylamine.

Thiophen ring is constructed readily on pyrimidine by reacting β -halogenocarbonyl compounds with ethyl 2-mercaptoacetate (or 2-mercaptoacetic acid) in presence of base⁵. The synthesis of thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (3b) was accomplished by fusion of 1b with ethyl 2-mercaptoacetate. Compound 3b was also obtained by reacting 4-mercapto-5-acetylpyrimidine (1a) with ethyl bromoacetate in presence of triethylamine. Attempts to synthesise 3b by treating 1b with ethyl 2-mercaptoacetate in ethanolic sodium ethoxide at room temperature gave instead 4-carboxymethylthiopyrimidine (1i). In the latter reaction the initially formed 1j presumably underwent basic hydrolysis during the aqueous work up of the reaction. This presumption is potentiated by the fact that attempts to synthesise 1i by heating compound 1b and 2-mercaptoacetic acid in sodium ethoxide solution led instead to decarboxylation and formation of 4-methylthiopyrimidine 1f (identical with authentic sample⁶).

Interestingly, the reaction of compound 1a with ethyl bromoacetate in aqueous sodium carbonate at room temperature gave 4-ethoxycarbonylmethylthiopyrimidine (1j). Compound 1j underwent ready oxidation by the action of potassium permanganate in presence of sulphuric acid to thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-7,7-dioxide (3c). On the other hand, on subjecting thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (3b) to the same oxidising agent under the same conditions, the starting material 3b was recovered completely unchanged.

1

a; R=SH

b; R=Cl

c; R=NHC₆H₅

d; R=NHC₆H₄-CO₂H(o)

e; R=NHC₆H₄-CO₂C₂H₅(o)

2

f; R=SCH₃

g; R=NHNHC₆H₅

h; R=NHOH

i; R=SCH₂COOH

j; R=SCH₂CO₂C₂H₅

3b,c

3b, X=S, R=CO₂C₂H₅
3c; X=SO₂, R=CO₂C₂H₅

4

5

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Microanalyses were carried out at Microanalytical Centre, Cairo University. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Varian HA 100 spectrometer (100 MHz) using TMS as internal reference. Compounds prepared by different methods were identified by their m.m.p. and ir spectra. The starting 2-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-4-mercapto-6-methyl-5-acetylpyrimidine (**1b**) was obtained following the literature procedure⁶.

4-Chloro-2-(p-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-5-acetylpyrimidine (1b): Chlorine gas was bubbled through a suspension of **1a** (5 g) in acetic acid (50 ml; 25%) for about 2 h at 10°. The resulting colourless solid was washed with water and dried (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1b	120–22	80	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ClNO
1c	155–57	75	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O
1d	210–12	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂
1e	152–53	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ ^a
1f	100–01	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ON ₂ SOI
1g	251–53	35	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂
1h	227–29	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ^b
1i	119–20	35	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O
1j	150–51	80	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClN ₂ OS
1k	90–2	92	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
2a	266–67	90	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₄ OI ^c
2b	147–49	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ^d
2c	180–82	45	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
3	248–50	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O

*^δ(CDCl₃) 1.5 (3H, t, OCH₂CH₃), 1.7 (6H, s, 2CH₃), 4.5 (2H, s, CH₂) and 7.3–7.8 (8H, m, ArH). ^b(CDCl₃) 2.7 (3H, s, NHCH₃), 1.0 (3H, s), 5.2 (1H, s, CH₂NH) and 5.5–6.5 (4H, m, ArH). ^c^δ(ODCl₃) 2.7 (6H, s, 2CH₃), 2.75 (6H, s, 2CH₃) and 7.3–7.6 (8H, m, ArH). ^d^δ(GDCI₃) 1.45 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 3.0 (6H, s, 2CH₃), 4.5 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃) and 7.5–7.7 (4H, m, ArH).

4-Arylamino-2-(p-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-5-acetylpyrimidines (1c–e): A solution of **1a** (0.01 mol) and the appropriate aromatic amine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was left at room temperature for 2 h. The resulting yellow crystals were recrystallised from ethanol.

Hydrolysis of 4-(*O*-ethoxycarbonylanilino)-2-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-5-acetylpyrimidine (1e): A solution of **1e** (0.01 mol) in alcoholic solution of sodium hydroxide (prepared from 0.4 g sodium hydroxide and 20 ml ethanol) was refluxed for 15 min, then let cool and acidified with hydrochloric acid (3 ml; 90%). The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give **1d**, found identical with the authentic sample (m.m.p.).

Bis[6-methyl-2-(p-chlorophenyl)-5-acetylpyrimidyl-4]-hydrazine (5): To a solution of **1b** (0.01 mol) in ether (20 ml) was added hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) dropwise with stirring at room temperature. The stirring was continued for 3 h and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals.

Pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrimidine (2): A solution of **2f** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solid obtained upon cooling was then crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals.

2-(p-Chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-4-(2-phenylhydrazine)-5-acetylpyrimidine (1g): To a solution of **1b** (0.01 mol) in ether (20 ml) was added phenylhydrazine (0.01 mol) while stirring. The stirring was continued for 0.5 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid as pale yellow crystals.

2-(p-Chlorophenyl)-4,5-dimethyl-(8H)-pyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine (4): A mixture of **1b** (0.01 mol) and was (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as pale yellow crystals.

2-(p-Chlorophenyl)-4-methylamino-6-acetylpyrimidine (1h): A mixture of (0.01 mol) and ethyl glycinate hydrochloride (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as pale yellow crystals.

Ethyl-2-(chlorophenyl)-4,5-dimethylthieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate (3b): A mixture of **1b** (0.01 mol) and ethyl 2-mercaptoacetate (0.01 mol) was fused at 120° for 15 min. The resulting solid was crystallised from DMF as colourless crystals.

4-Carboxymethylthio-2(p-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-5-acetylpyrimidine (1i): A mixture of **1b** (0.01 mol), ethyl 2-mercaptoacetate (0.01 mol) and sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.23 g sodium and 40 ml ethanol) was left at room temperature for 0.5 h. After acidification by hydrochloric acid, the precipitate was collected and crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals.

Action of mercaptoacetic acid on 1b: A mixture of **1b** (0.01 mol), mercaptoacetic acid (0.01 mol) and sodium methoxide solution (prepared from 0.23 g sodium and 30 ml of methanol) was refluxed for 0.5 h. The solid obtained after cooling was crystallised from methanol to give colourless crystals of **1f**, identical with an authentic sample (m.m.p.).

2-(p-Chlorophenyl)-4-ethoxycarbonylmethylthio-6-methyl-5-acetylpyrimidine (1j): A mixture of **1a**

(0.01 mol) and ethyl bromoacetate (0.01 mol) in Na₂CO₃ (10 ml, 0.01 mol) was stirred for 0.5 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol as colourless crystals.

*2-(p-Chlorophenyl)-4,5-dimethylthieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-7,7-dioxide (3c)*: A solution of **1j** (0.01 mol) in chloroform (10 ml) and sulphuric acid (2 ml) was cooled to 0° and then to it potassium permanganate (0.01 mol) was added slowly in portions. The solution was left at room temperature, then made alkaline, decolourised with acetone, extracted with chloroform and evaporated to dryness. The residue was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals.

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